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Wheat-pea intercrop affects activity density and biocontrol potential of generalist predators

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Summary

Intercropping can increase biodiversity within crop fields and may reduce pest damage by facilitating the presence and activity of natural pest control agents. This study aimed to evaluate the effects of winter wheat-pea intercropping on the activity density of aboveground generalist predatory arthropods and their biocontrol potential compared with pure crops. Field work was conducted in a field experiment located in Gembloux, Belgium. A set of proxies for ecosystem functions were measured to investigate activity density and biocontrol potential of generalist predators. In general, wheat-pea intercropping affected positively activity density in comparison to sole crops, although taxa responded differently to crop type. Results of the predation rates' assessment indicate that the potential of predators to contribute to biocontrol was lower in wheat pure stand compared to pea pure stand and intercrop. These results suggest that intercropping wheat-pea may represent a valid strategy to favour generalist predators and enhance pest control in comparison to wheat cultivated as sole crop.

Key words: Biological control; carabids; generalist predators; intercropping; Rapid Ecosystem Function Assessment

Introduction

Complex agricultural environments may benefit natural enemies by improving the availability of alternative source of prey, nectar and pollen, as well as providing shelter and favourable microclimate (Andow, 1991, Landis *et al.*, 2000, Sunderland & Samu, 2000). Agroecosystems that support both trophic and structural resources within and outside of crop fields are likely to maintain robust natural enemy communities, having a greater potential for pest suppression within a crop (Iuliano & Gratton, 2020). At field scale, intercropping is one of the vegetation management strategies that promotes plant species diversity, likely creating more favourable conditions for natural enemy populations (Zhou *et al.*, 2013). Numerous agroecosystems advantages of intercropping have been largely documented in literature: improved and stabilized yields, improved soil conservation and fertility, weed control (Ghaley *et al.*, 2005, Lithourgidis *et al.*, 2011, Bedoussac *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, ecological functions of crop-

associated biodiversity in terms of pest biocontrol have been demonstrated in several intercropping systems (Hummel *et al.*, 2009, Xie *et al.*, 2012). Wheat-based intercropping systems have been extensively studied, and a recent review showed that while pests are generally reduced in such systems, their natural enemies are not necessarily enhanced (Lopes *et al.*, 2016). In addition, the response of different groups of natural enemies can vary depending, among others, on type of intercropping and crops investigated.

Focusing on generalist predators, they can contribute significantly to reduce the populations of herbivorous insects during the growing season in wheat (Lang, 2003), and complementary effects of epigeal predators and parasitoids appeared to be an important factor limiting the growth of aphid population in cereal fields (Schmidt *et al.*, 2003). Recognizing the importance of generalist predators as a fundamental component of the natural enemy spectrum for conservation biological control, it is crucial to gather more data from field studies in order to assess the impact of intercropping on their biocontrol potential in cereal-based cropping systems.

In the present study, we investigated the effects of the intercropping winter wheat-winter pea on activity density and biocontrol potential of epigeal generalist predators (i.e. carabids (Coleoptera: Carabidae), spiders (Arachnida: Araneae), staphylinids (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae)). Applying the Rapid Ecosystem Function Assessment (REFA, Meyer *et al.*, 2015), we measured a set of ecosystem function proxies relevant for biological pest and weed control within the crop. We hypothesised that the association wheat-pea would benefit generalist predators, hence enhancing their potential as biological pest control agents in comparison to the pure stands of the two crops.

Materials and methods

Description of the field experiment

This study was conducted at an experimental site located in Gembloux, Belgium (50°33'37"N, 4°43'35"E). This site hosts a long-term experiment established in 1959 to investigate the influence of residue management on crop yield, soil organic matter content and soil physical properties, where six residue management treatments are applied to a total of 36 rectangular plots (72 m × 10 m; six replicates per treatment) (Buisse *et al.*, 2013).

The current three-year rotation includes sugar beet (or silage maize), winter wheat and winter barley. For the purpose of the project DiverIMPACTS, four treatments among the six historical are considered: (T1) without organic matter restitution or importation, (T2) with crop residues restitution, one pig slurry application and one cover crop in the rotation, (T4) without any restitution and once cow manure application in the rotation, (T6) with crop residues restitution and one cover crop in the rotation. T1 represents an extreme system without any organic matter restitution or external input, while T4 is the reference system, because it represents a classic management under conventional agriculture.

In the season 2018–2019, an additional crop diversification strategy was implemented: intercropping winter wheat-pea was cultivated to evaluate the performance of the crop mixture in comparison to the pure stands of both crops. In this context, each plot was divided in three parts for each crop type cultivated during this season, resulting in plots 10 m wide and 24 m long. Winter wheat (variety “Apostel”) and winter pea (variety “FRESNEL”) were sowed on November 08, 2018. Wheat was sowed with 325 seed m² in the pure stand and 200 seed m² in the mixing, while pea was sowed with 80 seed m² in the pure stand and 50 seed m² in the mixing. Herbicide was used in wheat and pea pure stand, while in the intercrop weeds were managed mechanically. Nitrogen fertilization was applied twice to wheat pure stand (80 kg N ha⁻¹ + 75 kg N ha⁻¹) and intercrop (35 kg N ha⁻¹ + 55 kg N ha⁻¹) in April and Mai, 2019.

Data collection

Data were collected during May 2019 over a period of 48 hours. Activity density, insect predation and weed seed predation of aboveground generalist predators were measured following REFA approaches described by Meyer *et al.* (2015). In each plot, three sampling points were placed with a distance of 6 m from each other. In each single sampling point, four items for the assessment of the different ecosystem function proxies (see below) were placed at each corner of a 50 cm × 50 cm square.

Arthropod activity density was measured with pitfall traps, using 120 mL jars (7 cm high with a diameter at the mouth of 5 cm) buried in the soil and filled with water/salt solution. Once collected, predators were classified into different taxa (carabids, spiders, staphylinids), and the number of specimens in each group was counted.

Predation by both vertebrate and invertebrate predators was assessed using green artificial caterpillars made from plasticine (Howe *et al.*, 2009) 25 mm long and 5 mm wide (Low *et al.*, 2014). They were glued on small pads of wood and fixed in 90 mm-diameter polystyrene Petri dishes, previously sprayed with an aerosol glue and covered with fine sand. Three dishes with two dummies each were exposed in each plot. After exposure dummies were collected and checked for predation marks. Attack marks were attributed to either arthropod, mammal, or bird predators based on the collection of images from Low *et al.* (2014).

Arthropod predation was assessed by analysing the removal of insect baits (fly pupae, *Lucilia sp.*) exposed on the ground. Ten baits were placed into Petri dishes on finely sieved sand and buried flush to the ground. Vertebrates were excluded from the prey using metal netting with 1.2 cm² mesh.

To assess seed predation, the removal rates of weed seeds of different species varying in size and shape were measured. Ten seeds of the weed species *Sinapis arvensis* L., *Capsella bursa-pastoris* (L.) Medik., and *Anthriscus sylvestris* (L.) Hoffm. were placed into Petri dishes on the surface of 80 grit sandpaper lightly sprayed with an aerosol glue and exposed on the ground (Westerman *et al.*, 2003). Vertebrates were excluded from seed cards using a metal netting with 1.2 cm² mesh.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed with R (R Core Team 2018). Generalized linear mixed models were fitted using the function `glmmTMB` from the package `glmmTMB` (Brooks *et al.*, 2017). All the models comprised the two fixed factors “crop type” and “historical treatment”. In addition, models for predators’ taxa activity density and weed seeds predation comprised also “taxa” and “species” as fixed factor, respectively. For the activity density models, a negative binomial distribution with a log link function was used in order to account for overdispersion of the data. Models for predation rates (binary and proportional data) were fitted using binomial distribution with a logit link function. Interaction terms between the explanatory variables were included and kept in the final models only if significant. Models included a random effect for plots nested within block to account for any block- and plot-level random deviation. The Wald Chi-Squared Test through the `Anova` function in the `car` package (Fox & Weisberg, 2011) was used to test if the explanatory variables in the models were significant. Type III Chi-Square Test was used in the models with significant interaction terms. After fitting the models, pairwise differences among variables were tested using Tukey’s post hoc test through the `emmeans` function from the `emmeans` package (Length, 2018).

Results

Activity density of predators

The total number of generalist predators collected was higher in intercrop, followed by pure stand of pea and pure stand of wheat. The predator community was dominated by spiders (40.8%), carabids (38.8%), and staphylinids (20.3%). In general, wheat-pea intercropping had positive effects on the activity density of ground-dwelling predators in comparison to sole crops, although species groups responded differently to crop type (Fig. 1). Carabids activity density was significantly higher in intercrop (3.6 ± 0.4 individuals/pitfall trap) compared to pure stands of pea (2.7 ± 0.3 , $P=0.0366$) and wheat (0.7 ± 0.1 , $P<0.001$). Significantly more spiders were collected in intercrop (2.9 ± 0.3) compared to pure stand of wheat (2.1 ± 0.3 , $P=0.0341$), while no statistical differences occurred between pure stand of pea (2.4 ± 0.3) and both intercrop ($P=0.2154$) and wheat ($P=0.6810$). Finally, activity density of staphylinids was not affected by different crop types (1 ± 0.2 in wheat, 1.2 ± 0.2 in pea, 1.5 ± 0.2 in intercrop).

Fig. 1. Activity density of each taxa of predators collected in relation to crop type, measured as number of individuals collected per pitfall trap (mean \pm SE). Different letters indicate a significant difference at $P<0.05$ within taxa: capital letters for carabids and lowercase letters for spiders.

Assessment of arthropod predation rates

All artificial caterpillars could be assessed for attack marks after exposure. In total, 13% of the dummies were attacked, 43% of those showed attack marks caused by arthropods and 62% showed marks caused by small mammals. Attack rates on artificial caterpillars were influenced by the crop type. Arthropod attack rates caused were higher in intercrop ($11\% \pm 3$) compared to wheat pure stand ($1\% \pm 1$, $P=0.0179$) and pea ($4\% \pm 2$, $P=0.0711$) (Fig. 2A).

Crop type had a strong influence on the arthropod predation rates on insect baits. Predation rates were higher in pea, with $61\% \pm 2$ of insect baits predated, followed by intercropping ($50\% \pm 2$) and wheat ($9\% \pm 1$). Those differences were statistically significant between all the three crop types ($P<0.001$) (Fig. 2B).

Predation rates on weed seeds were generally very low and were not affected by the crop type (wheat: $2.7\% \pm 0.4$, pea: $2.3\% \pm 0.4$, intercrop: $3\% \pm 0.4$). Seeds of *C. bursa-pastoris* were more predated ($7\% \pm 0.8$, $P<0.001$) in comparison to the other two species (*A. sylvestris*: $1.7\% \pm 0.4$, *S. arvensis*: $1.5\% \pm 0.3$).

Fig. 2. Arthropod attack rates on artificial dummies (A) and arthropod predation rates on insect baits (B) in relation to crop type (mean±SE). Different letters indicate a significant difference at $P < 0.05$.

Discussion

This study aimed to investigate the effects of intercropping winter wheat/winter pea on the potential contribution to biological pest control by predatory epigeal arthropods compared to the pure stands of the two crops. A set of standardized proxies related to the biological pest and weed control were measured following the Rapid Ecosystem Function Assessment (REFA) approach. Our results show that crop type has an influence on the activity density and biocontrol potential of generalist predators and, overall, there was a positive effect of the intercropping wheat-pea in comparison to wheat cultivated as sole crop.

In terms of predators' activity density, we found that predators responded positively to intercropping. In fact, more individuals were collected in wheat-pea association than in pure stand of both crops. In particular, carabids were more abundant in intercropping compared to both pea and wheat pure stands, while activity density of spiders was higher in intercrop compared to wheat but not to pea. Finally, activity density of staphylinids did not differ between crop types. The higher predators' activity density found in the intercropping is consistent with the enemy hypothesis (Root, 1973), which states that generalist and specialist natural enemies are expected to be more abundant in more complex habitats. However, it has been shown that modifications that enhance habitat complexity may not have the same effect on different guilds of beneficials (Langellotto & Denno, 2004). This seems to be confirmed also in our study, where different taxa responded differently to crop types.

Although several studies demonstrated that wheat-based intercropping systems provided more efficient aphid population control than monocultures (Wang *et al.*, 2009, Zhou *et al.*, 2013, Lopes *et al.*, 2015), the potential contribution of generalist predators to this ecological function still remains little investigated. For this reason, a quantitative assessment of predation itself is also important, and the use of sentinel prey artificially placed in the field is a useful method to obtain this information (Lövei & Ferrante, 2017). In our study, the observed patterns on predation rates were generally in line with the predators' activity density. For both dummies and insect baits, we found the lowest attack and predation rates in wheat pure stand. Attack rates on dummies in pea were intermediate and did not differ neither to intercrop nor to wheat, and the results of the predation assessment on insect baits show that pea and intercropping have comparable levels of predation, much higher than those in wheat. These results are not easily comparable to those from other studies, because there is a large variability in terms of crop species and natural enemy guilds investigated. Cárcamo & Spence (1994), for instance, in a study with sentinel prey did not find any advantages from a barley-pea intercropping system for the predation pressure of carabids. Nevertheless, our results underline that the overall

effectiveness of generalist predators may be enhanced increasing the plant diversity within the field (Dassou & Tixier, 2016).

Concerning predation rates on weed seeds, no effects of crop type were observed. However, predation rates were overall really low and this fact may have prevented the detection of statistical differences between crops. Higher predation rates on the smaller seeds of *C. bursa-pastoris* are to be attributed to the increased pool of predators which can feed on seeds of smaller dimensions (Saska *et al.*, 2014). Based on the results reported here and on other observations, and considering the extremely low proportion of seeds predated, we think that it is necessary to extend the exposure time of the seed cards in the field, in order to be able to detect meaningful predation rates.

In conclusion, although these results were gathered during one growing season, they show that not only activity density, but also biocontrol potential of generalist predators benefited from wheat-pea association when compared to wheat cultivated as sole crop. According to our hypothesis, intercropping wheat and pea may therefore represent a valid strategy to favour generalist predators and support conservation biological control.

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